

COMPLEX THERAPY OF PATIENTS WITH GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS**Mehmani I.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Medical assistant***Mehmani V.,***Azerbaijan Medical University, assistant***Aliyev M.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine**Department of Therapeutic Dentistry Assistant**Department of Orthopedic Dentistry,**Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10226690>**Abstract**

Complex treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis involves phased treatment, the implementation of general therapy and a number of local interventions. The goal of management tactics for patients with this pathology is to achieve stable remission, and subsequently long-term stabilization of periodontitis. A factor in the further prognosis of the disease is the implementation of maintenance therapy with simultaneous monitoring of patients.

Keywords: maintenance therapy, generalized periodontitis, Tantum Verde.

An important component of maintenance therapy is the prevention of local inflammation in periodontal tissues. The purpose of the work was to evaluate the effectiveness of using the drug "Tantum Verde" in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis at the stage of local maintenance therapy. Materials and methods. Dispensary clinical and radiological dentitis of II severity, which were divided into two groups: control (used an alcohol solution of chlorophyllipt during maintenance therapy) and experimental (used Tantum Verde® lozenges at the stages of maintenance therapy). Results. Hygiene of the oral cavity Tantum Verde® in the form of lozenges. In patients in the experimental group, on the second day after removal of dental plaque and taking the drug "Tantum Verde®," the disappearance of pain in the gums, swelling, and bleeding of the gums was noted. non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug "Tantum Verde" in the form of lozenges at the stage of local maintenance treatment of patients with chronic generalized periodontitis. This medication has a complex effect due to its distinct analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects.

Numerous epidemiological studies in recent years indicate a significant prevalence of periodontal diseases among the world's population. They are observed in all age groups of the population, have varying degrees of severity and tend to progress with age [1–4]. In persons over 45 years of age, generalized periodontitis predominates. For them, the symptom complex of periodontitis is an integral part of a variety of systemic diseases. the presence of low-quality orthodontic and orthopedic structures in the oral cavity, abnormal attachment of the frenulum of the lips and tongue, anomalies in the location of the teeth, small vestibule of the oral cavity, etc., as well as general pathogenic factors (diet disorders, immunology, hypoxia, chronic intoxication against the background of changes reactivity of the body [12, 13, 14]. The protective-compensatory mechanisms of the periodontal complex and the human body as a whole determine the degree of prevalence and intensity of the

inflammatory and dystrophic process in the periodontium [15, 16, 17]. All this determines the need to adhere to a comprehensive individualized differentiated approach to supervision of such patients. A mandatory condition is to take into account for each patient with generalized periodontitis the action of pathogenic factors, the characteristics of the pathogenesis of existing pathological processes. Complex treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis involves phases of treatment, the implementation of general therapy and a number of local interventions. The goal of the management tactics for patients with this pathology is to achieve stable remission, and subsequently long-term stabilization of periodontitis, accompanied by the absence of an inflammatory process in periodontal tissues. Therefore, after the end of the first and second phases of treatment, it is very important for the further prognosis of the disease to carry out maintenance therapy with simultaneous monitoring of patients. in the body and periodontal tissues, as well as preventing the appearance of an inflammatory component in the periodontium. For this purpose, antiseptic and anti-inflammatory agents are used in dentistry in the form of oral baths, rinses, nasal applications and instillation into periodontal pockets. It is very important to choose a medication that has both antibacterial and anti-inflammatory effects.

Among many pharmacological agents, the drug "Tantum Verde®" (manufacturer Aziende Chimiche Riunite Angelini Francesco, Italy) for topical use, which is available in the form of a 0.15% solution and spray with a characteristic smell of mint and candies, deserves attention. Along with the antibacterial effect, it has analgesic and anti-edematous properties, since it belongs to the group of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs of the indoles group, which actively act on the pathogenesis of the inflammatory process in the oral mucosa due to benzylamine hydrochloride in its composition. The drug has a high ability to penetrate epithelium and can accumulate in effective concentrations

in inflamed gum tissue without toxic effects on the patient's body. Its tablet form is very convenient for use in patients at the stage of maintenance therapy. Due to the long stay in the oral cavity, the drug is absorbed by tissues, with 50% of the dose absorbed within the first minute, and the rest within the next five minutes. Benzidamine restores the integrity of the mucosal epithelium and increases its resistance to the action of local pathogenic factors, especially biological ones (viruses, bacteria, fungi). It blocks the proliferation of these microorganisms and suppresses their growth, which is very important for preventing the development of complications and exacerbation of the process in periodontal tissues during the stabilization of the process [18, 19]. To assess the effectiveness of the applied maintenance therapy, an examination and phase complex treatment were carried out, which included therapeutic, orthopedic, surgical interventions and follow-up for two years for 50 patients with chronic generalized periodontitis of II severity. All patients were divided into two groups of 25 each: control (used an alcohol solution of chlorophyllipt during maintenance therapy) and experimental (used TantumVerde® lozenges during the stages of maintenance therapy). objective dental examination with filling out a periodontogram, calculating hygienic indices according to Green-Vermillion (1964), HYG according to Rateitchak (1989), papillary-marginal-alveolar (PMA) index by Leus, Pisarev-Shiler test and X-ray examination (orthopantomography, cone -radiation computed tomography). The diagnosis of periodontal disease was formulated according to the classification of M.F. Danilevsky (1984). At the stage of maintenance treatment, all patients with chronic generalized periodontitis underwent professional hygiene and sanitation of the oral cavity, and, if necessary, correction of the individual hygiene algorithm. According to indications, systemic osteotropic treatment was prescribed and locally after professional oral hygiene - Tantum Verde in the form of lollipops (study group) or oral baths from an alcohol solution of chlorophyllipt (control group) for seven days. Maintenance therapy was carried out every four months. The assessment of the clinical effectiveness of maintenance treatment was carried out on the 3rd, 7th day after the appointment of local therapy, as well as 6, 12 and 24 months after the start of treatment. Statistical processing of the study results was carried out using the Student test [20]. Research results Based on a comprehensive clinical and radiological examination, all patients in both groups were diagnosed with chronic generalized periodontitis of grade II. Their clinical and paraclinical indicators of periodontal status did not have significant differences. The level of oral hygiene in patients at the beginning of complex treatment in general was mostly satisfactory and unsatisfactory. The Schiller-Pisarev test was negative in half of those examined in both groups. PMA according to Parma in the control group was 78.6 ± 2.88 and 77.6 ± 2.24 in the experimental group. The CPI for Leus was within 5.67 ± 0.12 points (patients in the control group) and 5.48 ± 0.16 points (patients in the experimental group). phase of treatment before the start of maintenance therapy, the level of oral hygiene in all patients was good,

the Shiler-Pisarev test was negative, the PMA index for Parma was in the range of 3.5–14.8%, the KPI according to Leus was on average 1.25 ± 0.14 points. In patients in the experimental group, on the second day after professional oral hygiene and taking the drug "Tantum Verde®", there was a disappearance of pain in patients on the second day and complete disappearance on the fourth. An objective clinical examination showed that on the third and seventh days after removal of dental plaque in patients in the experimental group, the gums were not changed in color, had no swelling and no bleeding during probing. persons) and bleeding gums during probing (12 people). To date, all patients in the control group had no inflammation or bleeding gums. The results obtained indicate a positive dynamics in the disappearance of inflammatory reactions in patients of both groups, but in the research group it was twice as fast. The Shiler-Pisarev test was also negative in all patients. A year after the start of treatment, an exacerbation of the pathological process in periodontal tissues was detected in one patient of the research group and two patients of the control group. All cases of exacerbation of chronic periodontitis were associated with exacerbation of existing somatic diseases in patients. The Schiller-Pisarev test was positive in these three patients, RMA for Parma – 48.8 ± 1.64 % (experimental group) and 50.9 ± 1.52 % (control), KPI – 5.33 ± 0.06 points (experienced) and 5.54 ± 0.09 points. In patients of both groups, an aggravation of the process in periodontal tissues was not observed. Two patients in the experimental and three patients in the control groups had complaints of bleeding gums when brushing their teeth and eating solid foods. The CPI was 5.33 ± 0.06 points (patients in the experimental group) and 5.54 ± 0.09 points (patients in the control group), RMA for Parma was 38 ± 2.24 % (experimental group) and 40.2 ± 2.12 % (control group). The Schillera-Pisarev test was negative in patients of both groups. There was a decrease in the size of the epithelial attachment to 0.5 mm in 12 patients of the control and 14 patients of the experimental group and to 1 mm in 10 patients of the control and 10 patients of the experimental group. Thus, the results of clinical and laboratory observation of patients with chronic generalized periodontitis of grade II indicate the effectiveness of the prescribed treatment. The use of a modern non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug "Tantum Verde®" of local action is advisable in the treatment of patients with chronic generalized periodontitis of the 2nd degree of severity during the first, second phases, as well as at the beginning of the third phase of treatment as a local supportive new therapy. steroidal anti-inflammatory drug "Tantum Verde®" at the stage of local maintenance treatment of patients with chronic generalized periodontitis in the form of lozenges. This use of the drug is more effective compared to traditional antiseptics, since this medication has a complex effect due to its pronounced analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and anti-exudative effects.

References:

1. Malye DIu, Antonenko MIu. Jependiologija zakrepljaetsja tkan' parodonta: vikovyaspekt. Ukrainskie nauchno-medicinskie moladizhnye zhurnal. 2013; 4: 41–3.
2. Baelum V, Lupez R. Periodontal disease epidemiology – learned and unlearned? *Periodontol* 2000. 2013; 62(1): 37–58.
3. Demmer RT, Papapanou PN. Jependiologicheskie patterns of chronic and aggressive periodontitis. *Periodontologija*. 2010; 2000 (53): 28-44.
4. Papapanou PN, Susin C. Periodontitis jependiologija: li periodontitis podlezhashhih-pereneseniyh, po-diagnozirovannyh, ili iz? *Periodontologija*. 2017; 1(75): 45–51.
5. Zabolotnye TD, Boryshhenko A.V., Markov A.V., Shil'evskij IV. Heneralizovannyj parodon-tit. L.: HalDent; 2011. 240 p.
6. Zabolotnye TD, Pupin TI, Boryshhenko A.V. Zapal'nye jekvorazhivanie parodonta. Lviv: HalDent; 2013. 206 p.
7. Karotyn ZH. Klinicheskaja otechnost' stanu tkanej heneralizovannogo parodontita prizakhvorjувannjakh skronovo-nozhnoshhelepnogo suhoba. *Visnik problemoj biologicheskoy i medit-syny*. 2015; 3(2): 356–8.
8. Ribejro F.V., Santos VR, Bastos MF, De Miranda TS, Viejra AR, De Figueiredo LC. et al. A predydushhaja studija na FAM5C vyrazhenie v obshej slozhnosti hronicheskoy periodontitis. *Oral Dis*. 2012; 18(2): 147–52.
9. Vysochanskaja Ju. Innovacii v oblasti parodontologii. Chast' pervyj *DentArt*. 2014; 1(74): 80-6.
10. Grud'janov AI. Zabolevanie parodonta. M.: Medicinskoe informacionnoe agentstvo; 2009. 334 p.
11. Tebloeva LM, Gurevich KG. Faktory riska razvitija hronicheskogo generalizovannogo parodontita. *Institut stomatologii*. 2014; 2: 54–6.
12. Danilina TF, Mihalenko D.V., Zhidovinov A.V. Sposob diagnostiky neperenosimosti ortopedicheskikh konstrukcij v polosti rta. *Sovremennye naukoemkie tehnologii*. 2013; 1: 46-8.
13. Isakova NM, Isakov PA, Kynina OS, Zakalata TR. Vlijanie dental'noj vkladki na stanmikroflory parodontal'nykh kysheh u patsientiv s heneralizovannym parodontytom. *Visnik mor-folohii*. 2016; 22(20): 332–5.
14. Obychnyj K.Ju., Korshunova O. Vlijanie materiala ortopedicheskoy konstrukcii na biologicheskoe soedinenie polosti rta.